

Production of integrated rice culture and aquaculture on saline coastal soils in West Bengal, India, 1982.

Production (t/ha)	
Summer fallow period Apr- Jun 1982	Kharif, Sep-Nov 1982
	CSR1 3.12
	SR26 B 3.20
	Assam (S) 2.88
Brackish water 0.65 fish and prawn	Freshwater fish and prawn 0.51

to 24 mmho/cm (see figure).

After the aquaculture harvest, monsoon precipitation (av 1,750 mm/yr, of which 80% occurs from Jun to Sep) lowered soil salinity through runoff and leaching. However, late, low precipitation during 1982 delayed soil desalinization. E_{Ce} had dropped to 7 mmho/cm by Aug, when one-month-old seedlings of CSR1, SR26B, and Assam (S) were transplanted in each plot. Standard cultivation practices were followed. As the monsoon continued, E_{Ce} declined to an average between 4.8 and 5.8 mmho/cm for the rice

growing season. During the rice season, plots were used to grow some freshwater fishes and prawns (*L. rohita*, *C. catla*, *C. mrigala*, *H. molitrix*, and *M. rosenbargii*), stocked at 23,500/ha.

Rice was harvested in late Nov 1982. Average yield was 3.1 t/ha. Fishes and prawns, harvested at the same time, yielded 0.5 t/ha after 83 d of growth (see table).

Integrating brackish and freshwater aquaculture with rice culture on saline coastal soils yielded 1.16 t fish and prawn/ha and did not reduce rice yield. □

Nitrogen requirement of rice nurseries

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Recent experiments show that modern varieties can be transplanted, without yield loss, as late as 60 d after nursery establishment, or about 30 d older than is generally recommended. Maintaining nurseries for that length of time brings increased fertilizer requirements. We studied the nitrogen requirements of rice nurseries at PAU farm in 1981 and 1982.

Soil was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.4; low organic carbon. 0.23%; and 87-8-86 kg available NPK/ha. Nitrogen was applied as urea at 60, 90, or 120 kg/ha in 3 equal splits: at sowing, and at 15 and 30 d after sowing. Ten kg P

and 15 t farmyard manure/ha were applied basally. Nurseries were grown on 10- x 2-m beds planted with 1 kg seed. Nursery health was evaluated visually and by measuring seedling height and dry matter production.

Ninety and 120 kg N/ha produced better growth and healthier seedlings, but results of those 2 treatments did not differ.

Forty-five-day-old seedlings grown at different nitrogen levels were evaluated for yield. Seedlings were transplanted and received recommended doses of 120-26-25 kg NPK/ha. Data show that the nursery grown with 90 kg N/ha yielded 600-700 more rice than the nursery that received 60 kg N/ha (see figure). Yields for 90 and 120 kg N/ha did not differ. □

Effect on rice yield of N levels applied to the nursery, 1981-82.

Folcystein as a biostimulant in rice production

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We evaluated the yield biostimulant folcystein, derived from L-cystein with 50 g ai/liter and 1.0 g folic acid/liter, for drilled lowland rice at Culiacan Experiment Station (CAEVACU), Mexico. A foliar spray of folcystein was applied 80 d after seeding (1 wk after panicle initiation) at concentrations of 0, 200, 400, 500, 800, and 1000 ml/ha, equivalent to 50 mg ai/ml derived from L-cystein and 1 mg folic acid/ml, in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Table 1. Effect of different levels of folcystein on rice yield, 1976.

Folcystein (ml/ha)	Treatment mean ^a (t/ha)
400	7.2 a
800	6.1 a
1000	5.8 a
600	5.0 b
200	4.9 b
0	4.8 b

^aAv of 3 replications. Any two means having a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. S \bar{x} = 496.95

Plots were 4.5 m² with five 6-m rows with 25 cm within-row spacing. Local variety Bamoa A75, with 130 d duration, was seeded at 80 kg/ha. Urea 46%, N was

Table 2. Doses and timing of application of folcystein, treatment mean, and statistical significance, 1982.

Doses (ml/ha) and timing of application ^a	Treatment no.	Treatment mean ^b (t/ha)
400 E ₁	3	5.9 a
200 E ₁	2	5.7 ab
200 E ₂	7	5.6 ab
400 E ₂	8	5.5 ab
600 E ₁	4	5.3 b
800 E ₂	10	5.2 b
600 E ₂	9	5.1 b
0.0 E ₁	1	5.1 b
0.0 E ₂	6	5.1 b
800 E ₁	5	5.0 c

^aE₁ = maximum tillering (45 days after seeding [DS]); E₂ = panicle initiation (75 DS). ^bAv of three replications. Any two means having a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. S \bar{x} = 189.5 kg.